

Several nomenclatural notes on Palaearctic Cerambycidae (Coleoptera)

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Abstract. Several new synonyms are proposed. A long-proposed unacceptable synonymy has been wrongly proposed again as a new one. The composition of one subgenus has been expanded. The correct spelling of one species name and one subgeneric name have been restored. One name is recognized as a type species name of the genus.

Introduction

Cerambycidae is one of the most studied families of beetles, but its taxonomic nomenclature continues to be updated annually. Several taxonomy modifications and remarks are proposed below. One old species name is accepted as available and valid.

Results

1. The type species of *Pachyta* Dejean is *Leptura octomaculata* Schaller, 1783 [as “*L. octomaculata* Fabricius, 1792”] (= *L. cerambyciformis* Schrank, 1781), by subsequent designation in Westwood (1838: 41). *L. cerambyciformis* Schrank, 1781 is currently included in *Pachytodes* Pic, 1891. So, *Pachyta* Dejean, 1821 becomes the correct name for *Pachytodes* Pic, 1891 (*Pachyta* Dejean, 1821 = *Pachytodes* Pic, 1891), and the species previously placed in *Pachyta* would be included in *Argaleus* LeConte, 1850. This would lead to a great instability since both *Pachyta* and *Pachytodes* have been used a lot in the literature. A Case could/should be submitted to the ICZN to conserve the usage

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of *Pachyta* and *Pachytodes* by requesting the suppression of the type species designation by Westwood (1838) and adoption of *Leptura quadrimaculata* Linnaeus, 1758 as type species of *Pachyta* Dejean, 1821, proposed by Thomson (1864), which has been accepted in the literature. The new name *Prorhagium* Krajčik, 2025b (type species *Cerambyx lamed* Linnaeus 1758) is superfluous. New synonym must be established: *Pachyta* Dejean, 1891 = *Prorhagium* Krajčik, 2025b, **syn. nov.**

I am very grateful to Dr. Serge Laplante for consultations.

2. According to Plavilstshikov's (1934: 169) note on *Rhopalopus*: "*Rh. heteromorphus* Jank. 1932 = *nadari* Pic, 1894". I was unable to detect a publication by Jankowski (1932). Most probably it was not ever appeared. So, the name "*heteromorphus*" was firstly published by Jankowski (1934: 95) as a probable synonym of *Rh. nadari* Pic, 1894: "Остается, поэтому, провизорно определить нашего усача, как *R. nadari* со знаком вопроса, ... " (It remains apparently identified our longhorn-beetle as *R. nadari* with a question mark). Each such identification of the species inside its detail description by Jankowski (1932: 96, 98) was accompanied with question mark: "*Rhopalopus nadari* Pic (?)" or "*R. nadari* (?)". So, the name *Rhopalopus heteromorphus* Jankowski, 1934 was not definitely accepted by its author as a synonym, and it does not meet the conditions of the Art. 11.6. (ICZN 1999) - *Ropalopus heteromorphus* (Jankowski, 1934) is a valid name of a species distributed in Kirgizstan, Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. The species was described once more as *Ropalopus mali* Holzschuh, 1993; *Ropalopus heteromorphus* (Jankowski, 1934) = *Ropalopus mali* Holzschuh, 1993, **syn. nov.**

I am very grateful to Dr. Boris Korotyayev for consultations.

3. *Leioderus* Redtenbacher, 1845: 110 was described together with a single species *L. testaceus* Redtenbacher, 1845:153 [footnote] (Art. 13.4. Combined description of new genus-group taxon and new species). So, *L. testaceus* Redtenbacher, 1845 (= *Leioderes kollari* Redtenbacher, 1849) is a type species of *Leioderus* Redtenbacher, 1845, see Danilevsky (1988: 215).

Sama (2000) agreed that *Leioderus* L. Redtenbacher, 1845:

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110 was actually described alongside the species *Leioderus testaceus* Redtenbacher, 1845: 153 (mentioned in a footnote). However, for dubious reasons, he considered it inappropriate to treat both of these names as valid and regarded *Leioderus testaceus* Redtenbacher, 1845 as unavailable.

Sama (2000) cites ICZN 12.2.5, arguing that a new generic name must necessarily include at least one available specific name; however, Articles 67.2.2 and 69.3 of the Code clearly contradict this.

4. According to Karpinski et al. (2025: 7): *Lamiini* Latreille, 1825 = *Dorcadionini* Swainson, 1840, “syn. nov”. The unacceptable synonyms were already published long ago by Sama (2008: 233).

5. *Dorcadion rufogenuum* Reitter, 1895 is used to be published with a wrong spelling - “*rufogenum*”: Pic (1909: 99), Plavilstshikov (1932: 192; 1958: 278), Breuning (1946: 129; 1962: 432; 1966: 751), Lobanov et al. (1982: 263), Danilevsky (1993: 48; 2002: 2; 2010: 252; 2020: 443; 2023: 170), Hua (2002: 205; 2024: 680), Danilevsky & al. (2005: 137), Hua et al. (2009: 454), Toropov, Milko (2013: 12) and others.

A correct spelling “*rufogenuum*” was published by Gressitt (1951: 335), Lin & Tavakilian (2019).

6. *Eodorcadion* (*Arenodorcadion* Karpinski, 2025: 9) was proposed with type species: *Neodorcadion egregium* Reitter, 1897 for a single species *E. (Ar.) egregium* (Reitter, 1897).

Besides one more species must be included in *E. (Arenodorcadion)*: *E. (Ar.) brandti* (Gebler, 1841b). It is so close to *E. (Ar.) egregium*, that transitional specimens are known in China from the environs of Ulungur lake. So, *E. (Ar.) egregium* (Reitter, 1897) could be regarded as a subspecies of *E. (Ar.) brandti* (Gebler, 1841).

7. The taxonomy position of *Phytoecia malachitica* Lucas, 1847 rests unadequate. Traditionally the species was regarded as a member of the nominative subgenus as *Ph. (s. str.) malachitica* Lucas, 1847 (Breuning, 1951: 362; 1966: 751; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 307; Danilevsky, 2020: 443), or as *Ph. (Opsilia) malachitica* Lucas, 1847 (Reitter, 1911: 270; Villiers, 1946: 140), or as *Opsilia malachitica*

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(Lucas, 1847) (Vives, 2000: 488; Jeremías & Pérez De Gregorio, 2024: 191). At last it was included in a new artificial subgenus *Ph. (Metallicophytoecia* Özdikmen, 2025: 1819) - type species *Leptura caerulea* Scopoli, 1772, despite the fact that *Phytoecia malachitica* has nothing in common with *Ph. caerulea* (Scopoli, 1772). The last position was supported by Lazarev (2025).

In fact *Ph. malachitica* is quite unique and characterises by exceptional set of characters: undivided eyes, unicuspid mandibulae, black elytra densely covered with strongly shining green or bluish scales, male pygidium without emargination. The species deserves its own subgenus *Ph. (Hoplutama* Perez Arcas, 1874: 151, **nom. rest.**) type species *Phytoecia malachitica* P. H. Lucas, 1847.

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